

PROBLEMS AND POSSIBILITIES OF ENSURING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract. *In the strategy for reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025, a comprehensive transformation of commercial banks with a state share in the authorized capital is recognized as one of the priorities for reforming the banking system. This makes it necessary to ensure the investment attractiveness of these commercial banks.*

Key words: *commercial banks, investment attractiveness, assets, capital, profitability, credit, inflation, devaluation.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫХ ПРОЕКТОВ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ.

Аннотация. *В стратегии реформирования банковской системы Республики Узбекистан на 2022-2025 годы комплексная трансформация коммерческих банков с долей государства в уставном капитале признана одним из приоритетов реформирования банковской системы. Это обуславливает необходимость обеспечения инвестиционной привлекательности данных коммерческих банков.*

Ключевые слова: *коммерческие банки, инвестиционная привлекательность, активы, капитал, доходность, кредит, инфляция, девальвация.*

Introduction

In the strategy of reforming the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025, improvement of the credit portfolio of commercial banks and risk management practices in their activities, comprehensive transformation of commercial banks with a state share, sale of the package of state shares in banks to investors with the necessary experience and knowledge on the basis of competitive bidding, as well as , reducing the share of the state in the banking sector by simultaneously reforming commercial banks and enterprises with a state share was recognized as a priority for reforming the national banking system [1] . This creates the need to study the issue of increasing the attractiveness of investment projects of commercial banks as an object of scientific research.

Research methodology

The methods of induction and deduction, expert assessment, grouping and trend analysis were used in the research.

Statistical data of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan and financial reports of Bank of America, National Bank of Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Ipotekabank and Sanoatkurilishbank were used as an information source of the research.

Analyzes and results

In the US, in order to ensure the attractiveness of investment projects of commercial banks, great attention is paid to ensuring the liquidity, financial stability and capital adequacy of banks.

Since the current liquidity of Bank of America is provided by liquid assets in the form of primary reserves, we evaluate the dynamics and level of its liquid assets (Table 1).

Table 1.

Dynamics and level of highly liquid assets of Bank of America in cash, percentage [2]

Indicators	2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.	Change in 2022 compared to 2020
Liquid assets, bln. dollar	157,4	161,6	380,4	2.4 times
The share of liquid assets in the volume of gross assets, %	6,9	6,6	13,5	6,6 %

From the data presented in Table 1, it can be seen that the amount of Bank of America's highly liquid assets in the form of money increased significantly in 2022 compared to 2020 and had a growing trend in 2020-2022. This is a significantly high growth rate, which is a positive situation from the point of view of ensuring the attractiveness of the bank's investment projects.

Table 1 shows that the share of highly liquid cash assets of Bank of America in gross assets increased by 6.6 percentage points in 2022 compared to 2020. This is a positive situation from the point of view of ensuring the investment attractiveness of this bank.

Capital adequacy of commercial banks is one of the necessary conditions for ensuring its investment attractiveness.

Table 2.

The weight of regulatory capital in the volume of liabilities in National Bank of Foreign Economic Activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Ipotekabank, in percent [3]

Banks	2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.
National Bank of Foreign Economic Activity	10,1	19,7	17,4
Ipotekabank	8,2	15,8	13,2

From the data of Table 2, it can be seen that the weight of regulatory capital in the volume of liabilities in the National Bank of Foreign Economic Activity increased in 2022 compared to 2021, but in 2022 it significantly decreased compared to 2020. This is a negative situation from the point of view of ensuring the investment attractiveness of the National Bank.

In Ipotekabank, the weight of regulatory capital in the volume of liabilities increased in 2022 compared to 2021, however, in 2022 it significantly decreased compared to 2020.

3-жадвал

**The level of indicators of profitability of assets and profitability of capital in JSC
"Uzsanoatkurilishbank", in percent [4]**

Indicators	2020 y.	2021 y.	2022 y.
Return on assets	0,4	0,8	2,0
Return on capital	3,8	8,3	11,3

From the data presented in Table 3, it can be seen that in 2020-2022, both the profitability indicator of assets and the profitability indicator of capital had an increasing trend in Uzsanoatkurilishbank. This is a positive situation from the point of view of ensuring the financial stability of the bank.

From the data presented in Table 3, it can be seen that the rate of return on capital in Uzsanoatkurilishbank grew at a higher rate (7.5 p.p.) in 2022 compared to 2021. This is explained by the fact that the growth rate of net profit in this period is higher than the growth rate of regulatory capital.

Current problems related to ensuring the attractiveness of investment projects of commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan are following:

1. The profitability of assets in commercial banks is low.

The analysis carried out above showed that the level of profitability of assets in large commercial banks of our republic is low.

2. Problems related to improving the quality of the credit portfolio of commercial banks.

As of August 1, 2021, the share of problem loans of commercial banks of our republic in the volume of gross loans was 6.2 percent [5]. This is higher than the generally accepted threshold level (5%) in international banking practice.

3. Low level of investment attractiveness of shares of commercial banks.

The high rate of inflation and the high rate of devaluation of the national currency hinder the attractiveness of investment projects of the shares of the country's commercial banks.

In our opinion, the following measures should be implemented to ensure the investment attractiveness of commercial banks of our republic:

1. In order to ensure the attractiveness of investment projects of commercial banks at the expense of increasing the profitability of assets, first of all, it is necessary to ensure the normative level of the net interest spread indicator (1.25%); secondly, it is necessary to ensure the normative level of the net interest margin indicator; thirdly, it is necessary to ensure the proportionality between the rate of growth of net profit of commercial banks and the rate of growth of gross assets.

2. In order to eliminate the negative impact of problems related to the improvement of the quality of the credit portfolio of commercial banks on the attractiveness of their investment projects, first, it is necessary to ensure the normative level of reserve allocations intended to cover losses from loans (1.0%); secondly, it is necessary to increase the level of diversification of the credit portfolio of commercial banks by increasing the weight of retail loans in the volume of gross

loans and improving the placement of loans according to the network characteristics of customers; thirdly, it is necessary to remove the responsibility for the credit risk of the government programs and the preferential loans granted within the framework of the commercial banks.

3. In order to ensure the attractiveness of investment projects of shares of commercial banks, first, by reducing the rate of inflation and the rate of depreciation of the national currency, it is necessary to put an end to the decrease in the real value of investments made in the shares of banks; secondly, investors' income from investments in shares of commercial banks should not be taxed; thirdly, it is necessary to ensure the standard level (15%) of the indicator of the profitability of the commercial bank's regulatory capital.

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